

POLYMER COMPOSITE MATERIAL WITH INHERENT FUNCTION OF DAMAGE VISUAL INDICATION

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ABSTRACT

The new concept of non destructive testing for polymer composites is presented by bio-inspired “bruisable” GFRP composite with inherent function of damage visual indication. Concept is undertaken by smart sensitive layer, based on fabric impregnated with a mixture of two suspensions — microcapsules with a leuco dye and microcapsules dye developer. The chemical reaction between microencapsulated leuco dye and dye developer is possible, if mechanical load brings to the burst of capsule shell, dye is released, and get into the contact with colour developer. Thus, the mark resembling a bruise of a human body is formed in the damaged place. For the sensitive layer colour with the better perception of visual response after applied load was selected. Minimal content of microcapsules for the sensitive layer to ensure maximal visual response after applied load was defined. It was defined that test temperature does not affect on kinetics of colour change. Presented smart sensitive layer could be placed on a surface or integrated into composite structure by the method of vacuum-assisted resin transfer molding.

1 INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, the use of fibre-reinforced polymer composite materials (PCM) in such industries as shipbuilding, aviation, energy, construction is common and understandable. The use of PCM is explained by their unique mechanical properties and it is growing every year. At the same time, the application area of PCM also grows, thus making the question about structural health monitoring more actual. Visual testing is the oldest and most common non destructive testing techniques, but for composite structures it is not always applicable. Especially for types of damages referred as barely visible impact damage, where small indentation on surface may lead to significant delamination or other internal damages. The general aim of the study was to improve exploitation safety and simplify visual testing process of polymer composites in constructions. In this work damage visual indication was implemented by colour changing in the place of applied overload [1]. An approach is undertaken by integrating microencapsulated leuco dye and microencapsulated dye developer into the fabric layer (sensitive layer). Before overload, the surface colour is neutral and different from that after damage. The use of two-component dye ensures that the components will not be in contact up to a certain moment, for example, up to a certain level of applied load. The chemical reaction between microencapsulated leuco dye and dye developer is possible, if mechanical load brings to the burst of capsule shell, dye is released, and get into the contact with colour developer [2-3]. Thus, the mark resembling a bruise of a human body is formed in the damaged place. General concept of the damage visual indication system, possible applications, and result of the previous work are summarized in Fig. 1. Damage visual indication system consists of leuco dye, developer, and basis. As basis different fabrics was used. In the previous works for the external application a nylon fabric was used [4]. For the manufacture of an internal layer like fibre reinforced polymer a glass fabric was selected [5]. In the present work some issues related with applications of the sensitive layer are considered.

The specific aim of the research was to develop smart sensitive layer with inherent function of damage visual indication and validate it in lab conditions. For this purpose, the following tasks were formulated.

- Develop manufacture technology of the sensitive layer and ensure on its repeatability.

- Select dye colour from primary colours to ensure better perception of visual response after applied load.
- Determine required amount of microcapsules for the sensitive layer to ensure maximal visual response after applied load.
- Estimate the kinetics of colour change upon load of the sensitive layer at different temperatures.

Figure 1: Concept of the damage visual indication system and possible applications.

2 MATERIALS AND MANUFACTURE OF SPECIMENS

Microcapsules with leuco dye and microcapsules with dye developer, as water based dispersions were supplied by *Papierfabrik August Koehler Ag., Germany*. The nominal concentration of the microcapsules in the dispersion is 40% (data from the manufacturer). Further in the work, this concentration was considered as maximal. As a base of the smart sensitive layer a nylon fabric was selected. Nylon fabric using rubber roller was impregnated on the teflon substrate with the mixture of two dispersions in the volume ratio 2:1. After impregnation, the nylon fabric was dried for at least 6 h at room temperature to remove the excess liquid. Nylon fabric before and after impregnation with microcapsules are shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 2: Nylon fabric before (A) and after (B) impregnation with microcapsules.

To ensure repeatability of the sensitive layer manufacturing method five times this procedure was repeated; before and after drying of the fabric it was weigh, the density values of the microcapsules on the fabric were compared. In the result, $40 \text{ g/m}^2 \pm 3 \%$ of microcapsules was observed on the nylon fabric. This method was applied for the manufacture of all specimens.

3 TEST METHOD AND REGISTRATION OF THE VISUAL RESPONSE

To obtain controlled visual response specimens were tested on compression with the ring indenter. For this Zwick 2.5 universal testing machine with a rate of 2 mm/min at a temperature of $22 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ was used. Applied load was ranging from 0 till 400 N to find necessary load for the good visible indication. Sensitive layer tested with different loads is shown in Fig. 3. For subsequent measurements, the load of 400 N was selected as minimal to ensure good visible indication.

Figure 3: Sensitive layer tested on compression with the ring indenter ranging from 0 till 400 N.

Visual response on the applied load was observed immediately, but to ensure that all released dye get into the contact with developer and colour reached saturation 2h pause before estimation was provided. The visual response measuring procedure included: scanning of specimens, data treatment in *Photoshop*. For a quantitative estimation, the *RGB* colour mode and the parameter *Mean*, characterizing the average brightness of the image, were selected [5-6]. The difference between reference picture (before compression) and experimental picture (with visual response) was measured (Fig.4). The value of *Mean* from *Histogram* was used for further data treatment. Described above data treatment procedure was applied for all specimens.

Figure 4: Data treatment procedure; A – scan before compression, B – scan after compression, C – difference of A and B scans.

4 RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

Selection of the dye colour. For the selection of the dye colour to ensure better perception of visual response after applied load following steps were done. Sensitive layers with different colour microcapsules (red, green, blue, and black colour microcapsules) were manufactured and tested. For the compression test 400, 500, and 600 N loads were selected. Sensitive layers with different colour microcapsules after compression tests are shown in Fig.5.

Figure 5: Sensitive layers with different colour microcapsules after compression tests.

In the result of data treatment was defined: the same applied load leads to different colour response for different colours. Sensitive layers with blue and green colour microcapsules showed a more bright visual response after applied load, (Fig. 6).

Figure 6: Sensitive layers with different colour microcapsules; colour response vs. applied load.

Determination of the required amount of microcapsules to ensure maximal visual response.

For the determination of the required amount of microcapsules for the sensitive layer to ensure maximal visual response after applied load following steps were done. Specimens with microcapsule concentrations from 2.7% till 40% were tested on compression with 400 N load. Sensitive layers with different concentration of microcapsules after compression test are shown in Fig. 7.

Figure 7: Sensitive layers after compression tests; colour response vs. different concentration of microcapsules.

The decrease of the concentration of microcapsules till 16% in the sensitive layers, by adding water to the dispersion before nylon fabric impregnation, did not affect on the brightness of the visual response, (Fig. 7). Thus, it is more reasonable to use ~ 20 % microcapsule concentration in the manufacture of the sensitive layer; the layer will be lighter and the manufacturing costs will be less.

Estimation of the kinetics of colour change at different temperatures. Sensitive layers were tested to estimate colour change (visual response) vs. time after load at different temperatures. Before the test specimens were laminated to ensure the "safety" of capsules, thus specimens were more "friendly" to manipulations, like transportation and fixating. Specimens were subjected to a load, causing destruction of the capsules. Immediately after applied load series of photos were taken, starting from 5 photos/sec and till 1 photo/min. The same procedures were implemented for temperatures -20, +11, +21, +38 °C. Typical visual response curve vs. time after applied load is shown in Fig. 8.

Figure 8: Typical visual response curve vs. time after applied load.

It was defined that temperature in the range from -20 till +38 °C does not affect on kinetics of colour change (visual response) after applied load; for all specimens maximal visual response was reached in 10-15 sec and the brightness practically remained unchanged.

5 CONCLUSIONS

In the present work a manufacture technology of the sensitive layer is proposed. Smart sensitive layer is composed of a nylon fabric containing microcapsules with dye and microcapsules with developer on its surface. In the result of the experiments it was found that blue and green colours ensure better perception of visual response after applied load. After decreasing the concentration of microcapsules in 2 times it is still possible to observe maximal visual response after applied load. Maximal visual response on the sensitive layer could be observed after 10-15 sec after applied load and the kinetics of colour change is not related with the temperature.

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